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COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF APPROACHES TO RESOLVING TAX DISPUTES IN UKRAINE AND GREAT BRITAIN

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ABSTRACT

The article considers certain aspects of building a strategy for resolving tax conflicts in Great Britain and compares it with the regulatory regulation of these processes in Ukraine. It is emphasized that the tax conflict initially manifests itself in the mismatch of interests of the taxpayer and the state, and its natural development becomes its development into a tax dispute, the traditional ways of solving which in the majority of countries of the world are administrative and judicial appeals. It is emphasized that the taxpayer can freely choose the appeal path immediately after receiving the tax notice decision. A significant emphasis in the article is made precisely on the foreign experience of resolving tax disputes, and the characteristics of legal instruments and constructions different from those available in Ukraine. A comparative analysis of the means of unifying approaches in resolving very similar tax disputes in Ukraine and Great Britain was carried out. The joint functional purpose of the precedent approach used in Great Britain and the institute of exemplary cases implemented in Ukraine in recent years is emphasized. The similarity of the purpose of the precedent approach and exemplary cases with the purpose of the mechanism of general tax consultations in the aspect of increasing the efficiency of resolving tax disputes is characterized.

Keywords: tax conflicts, taxpayer, HMRC, foreign experience, legal regulation

INTRODUCTION

Tax disputes regularly arise in many countries around the world. This situation is determined by the different attitudes of taxpayers and regulatory authorities to the tax consequences that occur as a result of different modeling of taxpayers' economic activities. The emergence of conflict situations in taxation arises from the very nature of taxes. Acting as one of the main sources of filling the budgets of various levels, they increase the economic burden on taxpayers. It is the importance of tax revenues, the importance of their receipt in time and in full that determines the fairly strict and structured legal regulation of tax relations in the vast majority of countries of the world (Wahab et al., 2023).

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Resolving tax disputes is an important and pressing issue for Ukraine, as it directly affects the integrity and effectiveness of its tax system. Having a fair and efficient tax system that ensures compliance, protects taxpayers' rights, and maximizes government revenues is critical to the country's economic development. In addition, the resolution of tax disputes in Ukraine has broader impacts on the country's overall economic stability and attractiveness to foreign investors. Investor confidence, foreign direct investment, and economic growth can be enhanced by a transparent and effective tax dispute resolution system.

The economic and legal trends observed in Ukraine in recent years necessitate the need not only to improve the regulatory regulation of tax dispute resolution procedures, but also to determine the possibility of implementing the positive experience of other countries into the national legal system. This need is also due to the integration processes that continue despite the ongoing military aggression against Ukraine. In this context, it is considered appropriate to carry out a comparative analysis of the methodology and strategies for resolving tax disputes in Ukraine and other countries of the world. This article is devoted to a comparative analysis of Ukrainian and British strategies for exiting tax conflicts.

A comparison between Ukraine and Great Britain in the context of tax dispute resolution is important because it provides insight into different approaches and practices. The use of precedent regulation in the British legal system is a significant difference between Ukraine and Great Britain.

The Ukrainian tax system can be improved based on the experience from the UK in terms of precedent setting, non-confrontational methods, and efficient dispute resolution strategies. Adopting best practices from other jurisdictions can help to improve the effectiveness, fairness, and efficiency of tax dispute resolution in Ukraine.

The purpose of the article is to conduct a comparative analysis of the strategies used by Ukraine and Great Britain to resolve tax disputes. The article aims to provide a detailed overview of the approaches used by these two countries to resolve tax disputes, highlighting the peculiarities of the subject composition of these relations, the doctrinal basis for regulating the functional purpose of their participants, as well as identifying the positive features of foreign regulatory structures and to identify the similarities and differences of their respective systems.

The target audience of this study may include various stakeholders involved in tax administration and policy making. While government is certainly an important audience, other stakeholders include policy makers, tax practitioners and professionals, the business community, academics and researchers.

The article followed a structured framework. Initially, we conducted a comprehensive review of the existing literature and established the conceptual groundwork. The methodology was then elucidated, and the ensuing results were subjected to thorough analysis. The paper's closure encompassed a discussion of the findings, accompanied by practical and theoretical implications as well as acknowledged limitations. Ultimately, we concluded by outlining potential avenues for future research.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In scientific literature, the issue of resolving tax disputes is always quite relevant, which causes a significant number of scientific works devoted to this topic. They can be classified according to various criteria, such as geography of occurrence, type of taxpayer, reason for occurrence, solution path, consequences, and others. For example, a significant part of scientific works (Miller & Oats, 2006; Avi-Yonah, 2000; Dagan,2004) is devoted to the elimination of double taxation. This category of works

discloses in quite detail the issue of building global mechanisms for the elimination of double taxation and only touches upon the procedures for resolving tax disputes in a procedural sense.

In Ukraine, such scientists as O.Y. Buchynskiy (2019), O.O. Golovashevych (2020), I. M. Berezenko (2020), A. V. Lohvyn (2020), O.M. Duvanskyi (2012), M.V. Zhernakov (2015), I.Ya. Olender (2020), A.A. Rozdaybida (2015), E.A. Usenko (2010), R.F. Khanova (2014) and others dealt with the issue of tax dispute resolution and tax debt repayment. In their works, the issue of the emergence of tax conflicts, their development, the transition to the state of a tax dispute and their resolution at the national level was investigated. At their works also attention is paid to the procedures for the application of national coercive measures, which are used in the process of harmonizing the positions of supervisory authorities and taxpayers.

It should be emphasized that, despite the considerable number of scientific studies of aspects related to the resolution of tax disputes, there is still a lack of comparative researches on the border of national regulation of these issues in Ukraine and other countries of the world. Certain aspects of building an effective system of bodies capable of efficiently, quickly and economically resolving tax disputes remain insufficiently researched. Among the numerous scientific works dedicated to the study of various aspects of the implementation of traditional administrative and judicial mechanisms for the resolution of tax disputes, there is a lack of research on the strategy of choosing the appropriate way of resolving tax disputes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A comprehensive analysis of the rules of the tax system in Ukraine and Great Britain was conducted, providing reliable and well-supported information for further research or reference purposes, by using different methods. The first step was to clearly define the research objectives, which were to compare and analyze the tax system rules in Ukraine and Great Britain. An extensive literature review was conducted to gather information regarding the two taxing systems. Academic papers, government publications, reports from international organizations and reputable tax consulting sources were analyzed. To ensure the accuracy and credibility of the information obtained, several reliable and authoritative sources were selected and examined to extract relevant information regarding the tax system rules in Ukraine and Great Britain.

In order to facilitate a comprehensive analysis of the tax systems in Ukraine and Great Britain, it is necessary to evaluate them on the basis of the following key criteria: Types of Taxes, Tax Administration, Personal Taxation, Corporate Taxation, and Value Added Tax (VAT). Looking at these specific criteria will allow us to better understand the similarities and differences between the tax systems of the two countries. (see Table 1, *Source: formed by the authors according to Ukrainian Tax Guide, 2022; GOV.UK, 2022; PwC, 2021; Deloitte, 2021; Oxford University Centre for Business Taxation, 2020; Castagna, 2023*).

Table 1. The analysis of the rules of the tax system in Ukraine and Great Britain

Country Criteria	Ukraine	Great Britain
Tax Types	Ukraine has several types of taxes, including personal income tax, corporate income tax, value-added tax (VAT), excise tax, and property tax. These taxes are levied at different rates and play a significant role in generating revenue for the government.	In the UK there are several types of taxes that are levied on different aspects of the economy and the finances of citizens. The main ones are: Income Tax, Corporation Tax, Value Added Tax, Inheritance Tax, Estate Tax, Excise Duty, Capital Gains Tax, National Insurance,

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		Business Tax, Air Passenger Duty. These are just some of the main taxes that exist in the UK. The tax system may change over time depending on the economic and political situation.
Tax Administration	The State Tax Service of Ukraine is responsible for tax administration, including tax collection, enforcement, and taxpayer registration. The tax system in Ukraine has been reformed in recent years to increase transparency, simplify procedures, and reduce opportunities for corruption.	HMRC is responsible for administering the tax system. It collects tax, enforces compliance and provides advice to taxpayers. The UK tax system aims to strike a balance between efficient tax collection and taxpayer rights.
Personal Taxation	In Ukraine, there are personal income taxes such as personal income tax (PIT) and military duty. There are also additional taxes on certain types of income, such as winnings tax and others. PIT rates depend on income levels and are subject to change depending on changes in tax legislation. Ukraine provides certain privileges and exemptions from taxation for certain categories of the population, such as disabled persons and veterans. Personal income is subject to mandatory declaration and individuals are required to declare their income and file tax returns.	The UK has a more diverse system of taxation of individuals, including Income Tax, National Insurance, Capital Gains Tax, Inheritance Tax and others. Tax rates in the UK may also vary depending on the level of income and type of tax. The UK also provides certain exemptions and reliefs, especially for lower incomes, as well as for certain categories of workers, such as the self-employed. The UK also requires individuals to declare their income and pay their own taxes. However, the accounting system could be more developed and easily accessible.
Corporate Taxation	Corporate income tax: Ukraine has a corporate income tax system, where the main tax is the income tax. The corporate tax rate is 18%, but certain industries, such as agricultural production and IT, may benefit from lower rates or exemptions. Investment income tax: Ukraine provides certain incentives for investments and innovative projects, including tax credits and exemptions. Reporting system: Companies are required to report on their financial activities and tax liabilities by filing annual financial statements and tax returns.	Corporation tax is payable on the profits of companies operating in the UK. The main rate of corporation tax is currently 19%, but there are plans to increase this over the coming years. The UK tax system provides various incentives, allowances and reliefs to encourage business growth. Tax exemptions: The UK provides certain tax exemptions and credits for businesses engaged in research and innovation. Tax reporting: Businesses in the UK are also required to file annual financial statements and tax returns for reporting to the authorities.
Value-Added Tax (VAT)	Ukraine levies VAT on the supply of goods and services. The standard VAT rate is 20%, with reduced rates of 7% (VAT rate for medical devices, medicines, excursion services for museum visitors, screening of original works, adapted films, temporary accommodation services) and 0% (export rate) applicable to certain goods and services. VAT-registered businesses can generally deduct input VAT paid on purchases from their VAT liability.	The supply of goods and services is subject to the UK VAT system. The standard VAT rate is 20%, while for certain goods and services, such as tourism and accommodation, the rate is reduced to 5%. A zero rate applies to exported goods and most food products. There are exceptions for certain goods and services, and there are standard and reduced rates. VAT-registered businesses can claim input tax credits and must submit regular VAT returns.

Based on this analysis, it is necessary to examine the aspects of tax dispute resolution that may arise as a result of unsatisfactory decisions of supervisory authorities. This research will reveal the

different procedures and approaches to resolving tax disputes in Ukraine and the United Kingdom, allowing for a comprehensive comparison of their effectiveness and adherence to the principles of fairness and impartiality.

RESULTS

Aspects of resolving tax disputes that may arise as a result of a taxpayer receiving a decision from a supervisory authority that does not satisfy the taxpayer.

The tax conflict initially manifests itself in the mismatch of interests of the taxpayer and the state or territorial community, which are usually represented by the authorized controlling bodies of the country. The natural development of such a conflict of interests is the formalization of the tax conflict and its development into a tax dispute, the traditional ways of resolving which in the vast majority of countries are administrative and judicial appeals against the relevant decision of the controlling body.

Ukraine is no exception in this case. Ukrainian tax legislation provides the possibility for taxpayers to appeal the decisions of controlling bodies in an administrative or judicial procedure. It's quite important in this case, that the taxpayer can freely choose the appeal way immediately after receiving the tax notice–decision (Britchenko et al., 2022). Unlike Ukraine, in some other countries, a judicial appeal can be applied only after using the administrative appeal mechanism. It is quite logical that if the payer is prohibited from going to court before going through the administrative appeal procedure, his constitutional right to judicial protection is violated, which is unacceptable in modern democracies.

Within the framework of this article, we will not detail and compare the procedures for conducting tax audits in Ukraine and Great Britain, but will focus specifically on the aspects of resolving tax disputes that may arise as a result of a taxpayer receiving a decision from a supervisory authority that does not satisfy him. At the same time, the main emphasis will be placed on the foreign experience of resolving tax disputes, the characteristics of legal instruments and constructions that are different from those available in Ukraine.

In Great Britain, both of the above methods of resolving tax disputes also apply. Since recently, HM Revenue & Customs (hereinafter HMRC) has been the main entity in this country dealing with tax compliance issues by taxpayers (GOV.UK, 2022). In fact, it is the UK's tax, payment and customs authority. It was established by an Act of Parliament in 2005 as a new department to replace the Department of Revenue, Customs and Excise. It must be distinguished from the ministerial department which was created under the Commissioners for Revenue and Customs Act (CRCA) in 2005 and which replaced the Revenue, Customs and Excise Department.

HMRC is accountable to Parliament and expenditure on its operation is controlled by the UK Chancellor of the Exchequer. At first glance, the activity of this body is similar in its direction to the activity of the State Tax Service of Ukraine. HMRC is authorized to carry out audits regarding the payment of any taxes, the proper implementation of accounting records, the formation and submission of tax reporting documents, etc (Reilly, 2023). At the same time, strategic tax policy is formed by the Treasury, and HMRC is engaged in its support and implementation.

In contrast to the designation of the State Fiscal Service of Ukraine, the HRMC is entrusted with significantly more functions. In addition to the direct administration of taxes and fees, which is carried out in the most efficient and taxpayer-oriented way, this organization is engaged in:

- a) administration of other mandatory payments (for example, payment for illness, payment for pregnancy and childbirth, etc.);
- b) administration of child benefit;
- c) promotion of legal international trade, protection of fiscal, economic, social security of Great Britain, etc.

In fact, HMRC's activities are guided by a number of priority tasks, which include facilitating the correct taxation and making it more difficult to break the tax law. HMRC oversees the fight against money laundering, supports the government's broad economic objectives through a robust, flexible system of tax administration, responsible for ensuring that almost all taxes and duties are fully collected. That is why the HRMC is also entrusted with the duties of consideration and resolution of tax disputes and tax conflicts.

It is significant that in Great Britain taxpayers are allowed to challenge a wider range of documents than in Ukraine. In addition to the direct decision on the need to pay an additional amount of tax and fines, it is allowed to appeal the decision on the application of a specific tax benefit or a request for information on economic activity in a separate procedure.

When a tax conflict is formalized and a tax dispute arises, HMRC uses a tax dispute resolution management strategy. It was first published in 2014 and updated in 2017 (HM Revenue & Customs, 2014). The strategy provides internal mechanisms for managing the activities of this body. As a result, the approximate order of decision-making regarding the resolution of tax disputes is summarized.

One of the main priorities when the participants in a tax dispute choose a method of its resolution is to ensure an honest and impartial consideration of it. This guideline is used by both taxpayers and HMRC. In the event of a disagreement between the taxpayer and HMRC, the former may apply an administrative review of HMRC's decision. Alternatively, they can appeal through a tribunal or court (HM Revenue & Customs, 2017)

It is worth emphasizing that HMRC specialists during the implementation of control measures give taxpayers the opportunity to correct the shortcomings of their activities without formalizing a tax dispute. However, disputes regarding the amount of tax or the timing of its payment are common and inherent in relations regarding tax administration. Often, they arise as a result of different views on the interpretation of life circumstances regulated by tax legislation. The vast majority of such disputes in the UK are resolved through negotiations between HMRC and the payer or through the administrative appeals process.

However, there are still a lot of cases that are resolved in court. For the clearest coordination of the actions of regulatory authorities and taxpayers in Great Britain in 2007 was adopted a Litigation and Settlement Strategy (LSS) (HM Revenue & Customs, 2011), which was improved and updated in 2017. This strategy is fundamental for resolving tax disputes between HMRC and the taxpayer. In this case, the controlling body applies civil legal processes and procedures in accordance with the legislation to resolve the tax dispute.

In fact, the LLS strategy is used to resolve tax disputes regarding the payment of any taxes in Great Britain, regardless of their legal nature and type (direct, indirect, property, income, etc.). At the same time, within the framework of this strategy, an extended interpretation of the "dispute" category is applied. This allows the supervisory body to call a "dispute" not only the consideration of formalized tax disputes when it does not have a single vision with the taxpayer regarding the time of payment or the amount of tax, but also cases of obtaining additional information by the supervisory body to form an idea about the legality of the taxpayer's actions.

In contrast to the Ukrainian approach to court appeals, Great Britain approaches the definition of the term "litigation" in a different way within the framework of the application of the LLS strategy. Traditionally, in Ukrainian legal doctrine, a judicial process is understood as the process of resolving a dispute between participants with an appeal to a special body – a court. In Great Britain, at first glance, as part of the judicial process, there is also an appeal to an independent authority to resolve a tax dispute, but in addition to the court, such an authority can be a tribunal. Common law actions or applications for judicial review are also included in the "litigation" category.

It is important to keep in mind that the LSS strategy does not address issues related to the conduct of statutory audits. It also does not apply to debt recovery disputes, employment or commercial litigation in which HMRC is a party.

Any dispute that went beyond the agreement of the positions of the controlling body and the payer to the level of court proceedings requires significant financial costs from both the taxpayer and the controlling body. In other words, resolving tax disputes in court is simply expensive. That is why one of the functional goals that were set during the development and implementation of the LSS strategy in HMRC's activities was the formation of conditions that significantly reduce the likelihood of situations that could lead to a dispute.

On the other hand, the purpose of controlling bodies in both Ukraine and Great Britain is to ensure the fiscal goal. This presupposes the focus of their activities on obtaining the best income of the state and territorial communities from the payment of taxes and fees. But in modern democracies, such activity must be fully and completely based on the requirements of the law, use the given powers fairly and consistently (Levchenko et al., 2021). From these points of view, the formalization of a tax dispute by a controlling body (giving the dispute the features of a tax dispute that must be resolved within the framework of one of the procedures provided for by the current legislation), its consideration and resolution contributes to ensuring the best practical profit for the state.

The precedent regulation as a fundamental difference between Ukrainian and British legal regulation

The fundamental difference between Ukrainian and British legal regulation is the application of precedent regulation in the latter case. HMRC experts emphasize: "The objective of ensuring the best return for the Treasury requires consideration not only of the tax in dispute itself, but also – in circumstances where a precedent may be set or where HMRC is trying to influence the behavior of entities – potential tax liabilities of the same or other subjects" (HM Revenue & Customs, 2017).

Unlike the British model of resolving tax disputes, where the very fact of a court decision is prejudicial to the resolution of similar cases in the future, in Ukraine this issue is resolved by other methods. Two legal mechanisms make it possible to achieve unification of approaches in resolving very similar tax disputes in Ukraine. The first of them is tax advice.

This mechanism has been used for a long time and is carried out on two levels – individual and consolidated (Sardak et al., 2021). At the individual level, the taxpayer applies to the supervisory authority for an official clarification on how he needs to act when taxing a specific transaction. In the event that his actions fully correspond to the individual tax advice provided to him by control bodies, but as a result it turns out that he acted illegally, he will not be penalized. In fact, the institute of individual tax consultations provides a protective function for the taxpayer.

In the course of further systematization of the legal positions reflected in individual tax consultations, the Ukrainian supervisory authorities issue general tax consultations, which have a wider range of subjects on which they extend their effect. In a certain way, the institute of tax consultations allows to achieve goals similar to countries with a precedent legal system. Moreover, this is done at an earlier stage of the development of tax conflicts – before the judicial review of the tax dispute.

The second mechanism, the purpose of which is to unify approaches in resolving very similar tax disputes, appeared relatively recently. It is about the Institute of Exemplary Cases, introduced in Ukraine in 2017. Ukrainian legislation defines a typical administrative case as exemplary, which is accepted for proceedings by the Supreme Court as a court of first instance for rendering an exemplary decision (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2005). In turn, administrative cases that meet a number of conditions are included in the circle of typical ones:

- 1) the plaintiffs stated similar demands;
- 2) the defendant is the same subject of authority;
- 3) the dispute arose on similar grounds in relations governed by the same rules of law (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2005).

In fact, the institute of model cases fulfills the function of unifying court cases and at the same time contributes to speeding up the consideration of administrative jurisdiction disputes. Thanks to its appearance, a 2.5-fold speedup of consideration of typical cases was achieved in comparison with the resolution of other administrative cases (Kuybida, 2021). It is also worth emphasizing that the institute of model cases is not a purely Ukrainian invention, because the idea of its introduction was born in 2009 during professional meetings of Ukrainian and German judges (The Center for Judicial Studies, 2009). The emergence and development of this institute in Ukraine shows the positive practice of involving foreign experience in resolving administrative, in particular, tax disputes.

In Great Britain, when considering tax disputes, HMRC implements the principle of economy. A similar principle exists in Ukrainian tax legislation and provides for the establishment of taxes and fees, the volume of revenues from the payment of which to the budget significantly exceeds the costs of their administration (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2010). A similar content is provided in the British LSS strategy, because the supervisory authority will not consider a tax dispute if it does not provide the best income for the Treasury. In line with this approach, HMRC tries wherever possible to resolve disputes non-confrontationally. The results of HMRC's activities show that in most cases cooperation with the taxpayer is the most effective way to resolve a tax dispute (Perrou, 2023).

In the exercise of its control powers, HMRC, on the one hand, promotes a non-confrontational approach to the payer, but on the other hand, this does not become an obstacle to the effective and efficient use of other means in the event that it is not possible to establish cooperation. In their work, HMRC specialists apply a consistent approach to dispute resolution. Considerable attention is paid to professional standards, regardless of the final result (a final settlement under an agreement or as a result of a court proceeding). In any case, the approach to resolving disputes is based on the weightiness of possible negative consequences. If there are grounds to qualify the taxpayer's behavior as tax evasion, HMRC considers the appropriateness of more stringent enforcement measures and the possibility of a criminal investigation.

The British strategy for resolving tax disputes involves taking into account both the substance and the form of transactions performed by taxpayers. When resolving disputes, the supervisory body must make sure that both the substance of any decision leading to the resolution of the dispute and the manner in which this decision is implemented are fully in accordance with the law (HM Revenue & Customs,

2011). The LSS strategy requires the mandatory consideration of several points when choosing a way to resolve tax disputes.

First, HMRC will consider both future and immediate income streams in order to ensure the greatest practical benefit to the state or local authority. At the same time, costs and the deterrent effect on non-fulfilment of requirements by payers must be taken into account. Secondly, the controlling body necessarily takes into account the distribution of its own load. This means that when choosing the means of resolving a dispute, HMRC takes into account the potential consequences of the transfer of other open or prospective disputes. Consideration is also given to the potential impact of resolving a dispute in a particular way in freeing up HMRC resources to work on other disputes. In other words, if there are other tax disputes that could potentially generate greater economic returns than the current dispute, more resources are allocated to another dispute.

However, regardless of the presence of the specified discretionary powers, the controlling authorities in the UK must be guided by the fiscal interest. The British tax dispute resolution strategy takes into account both the economic and the temporal aspects of the efficiency of tax dispute resolution and in a significant number of cases the mechanism of out-of-court reconciliation of the positions of HMRC and taxpayers by means of an appropriate agreement is used, which ensures quite high efficiency. However, the Litigation and Settlement Strategy Commentary states that "HMRC will not compromise its view of the law in order to reach a settlement, and in this context, there will be cases where litigation offers the most effective and efficient way to resolve disputes (HM Revenue & Customs, 2017; (Moramarco & Orlandoni, 2020). In our opinion, this is how discretionary boundaries are constructed at the sub-legal level.

HMRC differentiates between the method of resolving a tax dispute by entering into an agreement with the taxpayer and going to court to resolve a tax dispute based on an assessment of the likelihood of being proven right. In cases of presence of reasonable grounds to believe that legal proceedings will be successful, HMRC will not agree to an out-of-court settlement if such a settlement involves the payment of less tax and penalties. In other words, if the taxpayer disagrees with reasonable arguments of his wrongdoing and does not want to give in as part of the out-of-court settlement of the tax dispute, HMRC will try to resolve the tax dispute in court. Conversely, when HMRC professionals consider it impossible or unlikely to win legal proceedings, there is an attempt to "share the load" between HMRC's position and the taxpayer's position on the amount or size of the penalties.

DISCUSSION

The research presented in this article contributes to the body of knowledge by providing a comprehensive analysis of tax dispute resolution strategies in Ukraine and Great Britain. By identifying the similarities and differences between these two countries, the study provides insight into the contextual factors that shape the effectiveness of tax dispute resolution policies.

Furthermore, the analysis identifies the role of trust and transparency in tax dispute resolution. By examining the importance of trust building measures between taxpayers and tax authorities, the study contributes to theoretical frameworks that emphasize the importance of interpersonal dynamics and relationships in tax administration.

The comparative analysis of Ukrainian and UK tax dispute resolution strategies has several practical implications for tax authorities in Ukraine. First, it is recommended to establish a dedicated tax dispute resolution mechanism that will provide a transparent and efficient process for resolving disputes

between taxpayers and tax authorities. This can help to reduce the pressure on the judicial system and provide a more expedient resolution for taxpayers.

Second, the introduction of alternative dispute resolution methods, such as mediation or arbitration, should be considered. These approaches have shown promise in both Ukraine and the United Kingdom, providing a more collaborative and flexible environment for resolving tax disputes. By encouraging dialogue and compromise, these methods can lead to mutually beneficial outcomes for both taxpayers and tax authorities.

In addition, the study highlights the importance of providing taxpayers with clear guidance and communication on tax laws and regulations. Improving taxpayer education programs and simplifying tax compliance procedures can help prevent tax disputes and improve overall tax compliance rates.

It is important to acknowledge that this study has certain limitations. The analysis focuses primarily on the tax systems of Ukraine and the UK, and the results may not be directly applicable to other countries. In addition, the study relies on publicly available information and may not capture the full range of tax dispute resolution practices in each country.

CONCLUSION

A comparative analysis of the strategy for resolving tax disputes in Great Britain allows us to draw a number of conclusions and suggestions. An unconditional asset of the British approach is the combination of economic and legal approaches to the organization of tax dispute resolution processes. The presence of sufficient autonomy of HMRC allows to successfully balance on the limits of its discretionary powers in the resolution of tax disputes in order to achieve the maximum fiscal effect in each disputed situation, combined with their optimal use of temporal and human resources.

The transparency of the work, that are done by the bodies, who are dealing with issues of tax administration, detection of violations of tax legislation, consideration and resolution of tax disputes, has an extremely important role for the effective filling of budgets. HMRC is accountable to the Parliament, expenses for its operation are controlled by the British Chancellor of the Exchequer, and its activity is similar in its direction to the activity of the State Tax Service of Ukraine. It was established that, in contrast to the appointment of the State Fiscal Service of Ukraine, the HRMC is entrusted with significantly more functions, which in its activity is guided by a number of priority tasks that involve facilitating correct taxation and making it more difficult to violate tax legislation.

Particular attention is given to the analysis of the UK's approved tax dispute resolution management strategy, which was first published in 2014 and updated in 2017. The strategy provides internal mechanisms for managing the activities of supervisory authorities. As a result, the approximate order of decision-making regarding the resolution of tax disputes is summarized. In particular, it is emphasized that one of the main priorities when the participants of a tax dispute choose a method of its resolution is to ensure an honest and impartial consideration of it. This guideline is used by both taxpayers and HMRC. In the event of a disagreement between the taxpayer and HMRC, the former may apply an administrative review of HMRC's decision. Alternatively, they can appeal through a tribunal or court.

The characteristics of developed and implemented in 2007 Litigation and Settlement Strategy (LSS), which was improved and updated in 2017, is given. It was concluded, that the LLS strategy is used in resolving tax disputes regarding the payment of any taxes in Great Britain, regardless of their legal nature and type (direct/indirect taxation, property/income taxes etc.). Within the framework of this

strategy, an expanded interpretation of the "dispute" category is applied, which allows the supervisory body to call a "dispute" not only the consideration of formalized tax disputes, when there is no unified vision with the taxpayer regarding the time of payment or the amount of tax, but also cases, concerning obtaining an additional information by the supervisor body for forming an idea about the legality of the payer's actions. Emphasis is placed on the economic aspect of resolving tax disputes, because any dispute that has gone beyond the agreement of the positions of the controlling body and the payer to the level of court proceedings requires significant financial costs from both the taxpayer and the controlling body.

It has been revealed that the British strategy for resolving tax disputes takes into account both the essence and the form of transactions performed by taxpayers. When resolving disputes, the supervisory body must make sure that both the substance of any decision leading to the resolution of the dispute and the manner in which this decision is implemented are fully in accordance with the law. The LSS strategy requires the mandatory consideration of several points when choosing a way to resolve tax disputes: a) consideration of both future and immediate income streams; b) taking into account the distribution of own load and resources, the potential impact of settling a dispute in a certain way on freeing up the resources of regulatory authorities to work on other disputes.

The introduction of a tax dispute resolution model similar to the British one in Ukraine can significantly reduce the burden on judicial authorities. Formation of a clear strategy for resolving tax disputes, which must be followed by all divisions of tax authorities without exception, is one of the primary tasks on the way to the harmonization of Ukrainian tax legislation and the legislation of European countries.

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